

Minimising the Consequences of Misplacing Your Umbrella

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Abstract

Whether one gets less wet by walking or running in the rain is a question often resolved by intuition; however, this can often be misleading. In this work, we develop a mathematical framework by modelling rainfall as a uniform field of water droplets and a pedestrian as a collection of planar surfaces. The total wetness is calculated as the total volume of water intercepted, first using a discrete Riemann sum and then taking the continuous limit for an exact solution.

The model accounts for arbitrary rain angles and pedestrian speeds, allowing for the comparison between different strategies' effectiveness. Analysis shows that, for constant travel distance, faster movement generally reduces wetness, though this effect depends on the rainfall angle. Jogging reduces wetness by approximately 15% and sprinting by approximately 30% when compared to walking in vertical rain. These results provide a definitive solution to the classic walking versus running problem and demonstrate the value of applying mathematics to everyday life.

I – Introduction

The question of whether one becomes less wet by walking or running in the rain is a familiar problem encountered in everyday life. While the solution to this question may seem apparent, informal reasoning through heuristic arguments frequently leads to contradictory conclusions: running reduces the time spent exposed to rain yet may increase the rate at which rain impacts the front of the body. Determining the optimal approach to reducing one's exposure to the rain requires a quantitative framework rather than intuition alone.

In this work, we construct a mathematical model describing the interaction between uniform rainfall and an idealised pedestrian. We begin by describing a simplified kinematic definition of rainfall and introducing a measure of surface wetness. The volume of rain intercepted by a moving surface is first approximated using a discrete time construction analogous to a Riemann sum, allowing the total accumulated volume of water to be approximated geometrically. Taking the continuous limit then reveals a simple geometric structure that permits an exact analytical solution.

Using this framework, we derive an explicit expression for the total rain exposure as a function of distance travelled and velocity. While the model requires certain idealisations, it captures the essential physics governing the accumulation of water on a moving surface. This analysis allows a direct comparison between walking and running strategies and provides a resolution to the age-old dilemma presented to people who have misplaced their umbrellas.

II – Mathematical Model of Rain

II.1 – Modelling Rainfall and Surface Wetness

To analyse rain exposure quantitatively, we must first derive an idealised model of rainfall which captures its essential properties while remaining tractable. Rainfall consists of many discrete droplets exhibiting variations in size, shape and distribution, as well as variations in motion due to turbulence and air currents. However, when considering the exposure over macroscopic distances and times, these small irregularities average out. It is therefore reasonable to describe rainfall statistically rather than tracking individual droplets.

We model rain as a uniform field of water droplets falling vertically with constant velocity. At any instant, droplets are assumed to be distributed uniformly throughout space with constant density, and any interactions between droplets are disregarded. Moreover, the external effects, such as wind or turbulence, can also be disregarded. This assumption now treats rainfall as a steady flux of particles moving through space.

The wetness of a surface arises from the physical collision of water droplets with the surface over time. Since we assumed that every water droplet is identical, the total wetness is proportional to the number of droplets which collide with the surface. We can then define a collision between a droplet and the surface to occur when their trajectories intersect at the same time. Therefore, the total wetness of the surface over a time interval Δt is the sum of all such intersections over this interval.

Because rainfall is modelled as a uniform field of droplets, the exact positions and trajectories of individual droplets do not need to be specified, rather, the expected number of collisions can be determined statistically from the droplet density, or the number of droplets present in an arbitrary region of space, and region of space swept out by the moving surface. Consequently, determining the rain exposure of a surface becomes a geometric problem by calculating the volume of rainfall intersected by the surface over time.

II.II – Discrete Approximation via Riemann Sums

To determine the amount of rainfall which comes into contact with the surface over a period of time, we first use a discrete time approximation. Consider a vertical surface moving horizontally from position A to position B with constant velocity. Rather than analysing the motion continuously, we divide the elapsed time into small intervals: Δt .

At time t , the surface, of area A , is found at a specific position p in space travelling at a constant velocity v . During the subsequent interval Δt , the surface advances a small horizontal distance $v\Delta t$. As the surface advances from p to $p + v\Delta t$, it collides with all the water droplets contained within the volume covered by the surface: $A(p + v\Delta t)$. This region is represented geometrically by a cuboid c .

At time t_0 , when the surface is at position A , the first swept cuboid, c_1 , lies immediately in front of the surface. Because the rain droplets fall with constant vertical velocity, the droplets occupying the next swept volume c_2 , at time $t_0 + \Delta t$, have descended slightly relative to their earlier positions. Consequently, when represented at a common reference time, successive cuboids appear slightly shifted upward, as seen in Figure 1. This displacement reflects the downward motion of the rainfall during each interval. However, the intercepted volume depends solely on the swept regions of space and is independent of how these regions are represented geometrically.

Figure 1

Repeating this construction for all successive intervals produces a sequence of adjacent cuboids spanning the entire distance from A to B . The total volume of rain intercepted during the surface's journey over this distance, $V_{(f)}$, is therefore approximately the sum of all such cuboids:

$$V_{(f)} \approx \sum c_i$$

The same construction can be made for a horizontal surface moving between the same two points, A and B . Rather than rederiving the approximation in full, we adapt the previous model introduced for the vertical surface.

Consider a new horizontal surface of area A , moving with constant velocity v . Over the time interval Δt , the rainfall intersected with the surface is no longer due to the surface "colliding into" the rain, rather the rain falling onto the surface. Thus, over Δt , the volume of rain which intersects the surface is a similar cuboid, which instead extends upwards from the surface, with height proportional to the velocity of the rain (specifically: $v\Delta t$, where v is the terminal velocity of the rain).

Subsequently, we can construct a similar sequence of cuboids extending upwards from the surface, however, since the surface is moving horizontally, each subsequent cuboid is slightly shifted horizontally. And as such, the total volume of rain intercepted by this horizontal surface, $V_{(t)}$, is again approximately the sum of all the cuboids:

$$V_{(t)} \approx \sum c_i$$

A person is approximated as an upright cuboid moving horizontally through this uniform rainfall field. Rain therefore intersects the two principal surfaces: the front face, as the body advances through the rain, and the top face, as droplets fall into it. Thus, the total volume of rain intersected by the person, V_T , is the sum of the volumes intersected by the vertical and horizontal surfaces:

$$V_T \approx \sum c_i^{(f)} + \sum c_i^{(t)}$$

With the vertical (front) cuboids denoted as $c_i^{(f)}$, and the horizontal (top) cuboids denoted as $c_i^{(t)}$. This representation remains an approximation due to the discretisation of time into finite intervals. Nevertheless, it provides a geometric representation of the accumulated rainfall on a person.

II.III – The Continuous Limit

Since the above approximation divides the intercepted volume into intervals of width Δt , to find an exact expression, we can consider the limit as $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$.

As Δt becomes arbitrarily small, the sequence of cuboids no longer forms a "stepped" geometry, rather, it approaches a continuous region. The small vertical displacements during each interval combine into a straight line, which when taken as the limit, the volume swept by the surface converges on a parallelogram, shown by Figure 2.

Figure 2

Geometrically, the volume of a parallelepiped is equal to the area of the end face multiplied by its horizontal distance. Given this, the volume of this parallelepiped (the area swept by the surface) is equal to the distance between A and B multiplied by the area of the surface, in this case, the area of the vertical surface.

Similarly, when $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, the volume covered by the horizontal surface also becomes a parallelepiped. As such, the total volume swept by the person is the sum of the two parallelepiped's volumes:

$$V_T = V_{(f)} + V_{(t)}$$

$$V_{(f)} = dA_{(f)} \quad V_{(t)} = hA_{(t)}$$

Where the front and top surface areas are denoted as $A_{(f)}$ and $A_{(t)}$ respectively, the horizontal distance between A and B denoted as d , and the distance fallen by the water droplets over the total period denoted as h .

II.IV – Generalisation to Arbitrary Rainfall Direction

To generalise the volume swept by a surface for any arbitrary direction of rainfall, we can first consider the implication of rain fall perfectly vertically. The volume swept by the top surface is proportional to the distance fallen by the rain over the total period. This distance fallen is in turn proportional to the velocity of the falling rain, or more accurately, the relative velocity between the falling rain and the surface. Since the surface is moving horizontally, its vertical velocity is zero, so the relative velocity is the velocity of the falling rain.

We can show this relationship by modifying the original model of the area swept by a horizontal surface. Substituting the distance fallen by the water droplets, h , with the equivalent product of vertical velocity and total period, $v_y T$:

$$V_T = dA_{(f)} + (v_y T)A_{(t)}$$

Now let us consider the addition of a horizontal velocity component to the rain. It is important to note that earlier it was established that the volume swept by the front surface is proportional to the distance travelled by the surface. However, motion of the surface through vertically falling rain is equivalent to rain moving towards a stationary surface. This distinction depends only on the chosen reference frame; the resulting flux remains the same. For example, a surface moving forward into the rain at 4 m s^{-1} is equivalent to the rain travelling backward into the surface at 4 m s^{-1} . In general, the volume swept by any surface depends only on the component of the relative velocity between the rain and the surface perpendicular to that surface.

Given this, we can also establish that the volume swept by the front surface is proportional to the relative velocity of the surface, $v_{(f)}$, and the horizontal component of the rain's velocity, v_x :

$$V_{(f)} = T(|v_x - v_{(f)}|)A_{(f)}$$

Again, substituting back into the original gives:

$$V_T = T(|v_x - v_{(f)}|)A_{(f)} + (v_y T)A_{(t)}$$

The horizontal and vertical components of the rainfall velocity are denoted as the x and y components respectively: v_x and v_y . These components are calculated from the velocity of the rain, v , and the angle, θ , of the falling rain:

$$V_T = T(|v \cos \theta - v_{(f)}|A_{(f)} + (v \sin \theta)A_{(t)})$$

Or alternatively using the distance between A and B , d :

$$V_T = \frac{d}{v_{(f)}} (|v \cos \theta - v_{(f)}|A_{(f)} + (v \sin \theta)A_{(t)})$$

Note that the angle, θ , is measured between the rain and the horizontal ground. For example, for perfectly vertical rain, $\theta = 90$.

II.V – Calculating Volume of Water Intercepted

With the above equation for the total volume intercepted by the person, the total volume of water intercepted, or wetness, can be calculated. As described earlier, we approximate rainfall as a uniform field of water droplets, therefore, the wetness of a surface, or the volume of water intercepted, W , can be statistically predicted using the droplet density, ρ , and volume covered V :

$$W = \rho V_d V$$

Rainfall is formally defined as the volume flux per unit area. Assuming that rain is a uniform field, the droplet density can be considered constant throughout the volume. Under this assumption, the droplet density, ρ , can be calculated from the rainfall, R , droplet volume, V_d , and velocity, v . This relationship can be expressed as:

$$R = \rho v V_d$$

Or alternatively, using the droplet diameter, D :

$$R = \rho v \frac{\pi}{6} D^3$$

Then, rearranging to find the droplet density, ρ :

$$\rho = \frac{R}{vV_d}$$

The terminal velocity of a droplet of a given diameter can be approximated by the following equation [1]:

$$v = 17.67D^{0.67}$$

Although, we can estimate the terminal velocity of a droplet of a given diameter, the average diameter of water droplets over an interval of rain is more difficult to calculate. Instead, these values can be obtained from instrument data. Below is a table of approximate average water droplet sizes for a given amount of rainfall [2] [3], and their calculated terminal velocities:

Rainfall Type	Rainfall, R (mm h ⁻¹)	Average Droplet Diameter, D (m)	Terminal Velocity, v (m s ⁻¹)
Light	1 – 2	0.001	3.8
Moderate	2 – 5	0.0012	4.3
Heavy	5 – 20	0.0015	5.0

With these, we can calculate the droplet density of a given type of rainfall. Below is a table of the calculated droplet densities for each rain type, as well as the droplet volume:

Rainfall Type	Average Rainfall, R (mm h ⁻¹)	Droplet Density, ρ (m ⁻³)	Droplet Volume, V_d (m ³)
Light	1.5	~210	5.2 x10 ⁻¹⁰
Moderate	5	~360	9.0 x10 ⁻¹⁰
Heavy	10	~360	1.8 x10 ⁻⁹

The values tabulated above can be substituted back into the previous wetness equation to calculate the wetness of a surface over its swept volume. Substituting the volume swept by the person into this wetness equation gives:

$$W = \rho V_d \frac{d}{v_{(f)}} (|v \cos \theta - v_{(f)}| A_{(f)} + (v \sin \theta) A_{(t)})$$

III – Conclusion

With a final equation for the total wetness of a person, a direct comparison between walking and running in the rain can now be made. The equation clearly shows that the wetness is inversely proportional to the velocity of the moving surface for a constant distance, d . That is, the faster a person is moving, the less time they are exposed to the rain over the same distance, thus reducing the overall water intercepted. On the other hand, a slower moving person remains exposed to the rain for longer, leading to a greater volume of water intercepted. However, this effect depends on the angle of the rainfall.

For rain falling at angles less than approximately 80° , the relationship is more complex: the minimum wetness occurs when the person's velocity is equal to the horizontal component of the rain's velocity, in which case, only rain falling from above contributes to the wetness.

This framework allows for a quantitative analysis of the differences between walking and running in the rain. Below are the calculated exposure (wetness) values for several strategies, where velocities are for the average person, rain is assumed to be perfectly vertical ($\theta = 90$) and the top and frontal surface areas are assumed to be 0.1 m^2 and 0.5 m^2 respectively:

Rainfall Type	Wetness from Different Strategies ($\text{mm}^3 \text{ m}^{-1}$)		
	Walk - 1.5 m s^{-1}	Jog - 2.6 m s^{-1}	Sprint - 6.7 m s^{-1}
Light	82	71	61
Moderate	255	216	183
Heavy	540	449	372

As seen in the table above, the faster a person travels, the less wet they get. On average, a person will get approximately 15% less wet by jogging rather than walking, and approximately 30% less wet by sprinting rather than walking, again assuming vertically falling rain. Whether this reduction in exposure justifies the additional exertion is left to the reader, however, these results conclusively demonstrate that running is generally preferable to walking in the event that one has forgotten their umbrella.

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